

Funded by the
European Union

EURL-PH-FWDB

EU Reference Laboratory for public health on food- and water-borne bacteria

Grant Agreement Number: 101244118

Project Title: EU Reference Laboratory in public health in the field
of food- and water-borne bacteria

Project Acronym: EURL-PH-FWDB

EU4Health Programme

Deliverable: D6.2 – A training plan for in-person training 2 –

Year 1

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Document overview

Deliverable number	D6.2
Deliverable name	D6.2 – A training plan for in-person training 2 – Year 1
Work package number / name	WP6 / Training
Task number / name	T6.1 / Organisation and delivery of in-person trainings
Due Date	M10 / 31 October 2026
Date of submission / version	08.04.2026 /v1
Dissemination level	Public
Authors	Federica Gigliucci, Guendalina Fornari Luswergh, Rosangela Tozzoli, Simon Bo Lassen, Vera Irene Erickson
Lead Beneficiary	Statens Serum Institut (SSI)
Project website	NA
The deliverable agreed with ECDC	03.04.2026 Cecilia Jernberg, Taina Niskanen

List of Acronyms

DL	Deliverable
EAEC	Enteroaggregative <i>E. coli</i>
EIEC	Enteroinvasive <i>E. coli</i>
ETEC	Enterotoxigenic <i>E. coli</i>
EU	European Union
EURL	EU Reference Laboratory
FWD-Net	European Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses Network
ISS	Istituto Superiore di Sanità
NA	Not applicable
NFP	National Focal Point
OCP	Operational Contact Point
RIVM	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
STEC	Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i>
WP	Work package

Table of Contents

Deliverable: D6.2 – A training plan for in-person training 2 –	1
Year 1.....	1
1. General information.....	5
2. Background and Rationale	5
3. Training Objectives	6
3.1 Overall Objective	6
3.2 Specific Learning Objectives	6
4. Target Audience and Participant Profile	7
5. Training Topics	7
6. Training Format and Methodology	7
7. Draft Agenda	7
8. Participant Selection Criteria.....	8
9. Invitation Procedure	8
10. Training Evaluation Plan.....	9
10.1 Evaluation Objectives	9
10.2 Evaluation Methods	9
10.3 Use of Evaluation Results	9
11. Training Materials and Dissemination	9
12. Logistical Arrangements.....	9
13. Annexes	10
Annex 1 – Draft Invitation Letter.....	10
Document review / approval (the coordinator).....	12

1. General information

This document outlines the training plan for the second in-person training activity of the EURL-PH-FWDB project. This WP aims to develop, organise, and deliver training activities aimed at expanding the knowledge and skills required to improve the current national prevention, preparedness and response plans, in alignment with the training activities of Regulation 2022/2371 on cross-border health threats.

Field	Information
Title of Training	In-person training on the identification and characterization of the different groups of pathogenic <i>E. coli</i>
Dates	07-09-2026 to 09-09-2026 14-09-2026 to 16-09-2026
Duration	Three days
Location	Rome, Italy, ISS
Organising Institution	Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS)
Contact Person (name, title, email)	Federica Gigliucci, federica.gigliucci@iss.it Guendalina Fornari Luswergh guendalina.fornariluswergh@iss.it Training-STEC-EURL-PH-FWDB@iss.it
Target Audience	Microbiologists and technicians who are interested in the characterization of <i>E. coli</i> pathogroups performing real time and conventional PCR.
Number of Participants	20 participants (10 per session)

2. Background and Rationale

The EURL-PH-FWDB workplan includes the training of Public Health laboratory staff through the organisation and delivery of in-person trainings on the different bacteria in the scope of the

EURL (Task 6.1). The in-person training will focus on topics related to the methods covered by the EQA or other identified disease network needs. The training activities are aimed at expanding the knowledge and skills required to improve the current national prevention, preparedness and response plans, in alignment with the training activities of Regulation 2022/2371 on cross-border health threats.

This training addresses identified needs within the network to:

- strengthen technical capacity of laboratories to identification and characterisation of diarrhoeagenic *Escherichia coli*
- harmonise laboratory and analytical approaches across countries
- support outbreak detection and investigation
- improve data comparability and reporting

The training builds on experience and needs identified through previous initiatives, including FWD AMR-RefLabCap, GenEpi-BioTrain, and relevant EURLs in food safety.

By providing hands-on experience with *E. coli* strains and commonly used laboratory techniques, the course contributes to strengthening national and EU-level preparedness for foodborne outbreak investigations.

3. Training Objectives

3.1 Overall Objective

The course objective is to strengthen participants' capability to identify and characterise diarrhoeagenic *E. coli* using molecular methods and to interpret results in a public health context.

3.2 Specific Learning Objectives

After completing the training, participants will be able to:

- extract high-quality DNA suitable for real-time PCR
- Perform and accurately interpret real-time PCR assays designed to detect virulence genes specific to the different *E. coli* pathogroups
- Differentiate between STEC, EIEC, Shigella, ETEC and EAEC strains based on virulence profiles
- Perform *stx* subtyping using conventional PCR
- Perform serogroup characterisation
- Understand the epidemiological relevance of virulence gene combinations

4. Target Audience and Participant Profile

The training is intended for:

- microbiologists and laboratory technicians
- staff working at national reference laboratories in public health or equivalent laboratories

Participants are expected to:

- have basic experience with diagnosis of diarrheagenic *E. coli* infections
- have sufficient proficiency in English to follow lectures and participate in discussions

The course is designed at an introductory level, progressing from theoretical concepts to hands-on laboratory exercises and analysis of results.

5. Training Topics

- Topic 1: Overview of the different groups of pathogenic *E. coli*
- Topic 2: Molecular profiling of virulence-associated genes characteristic of different *E. coli* pathotypes, including the potential detection and classification of hybrid strains.
- Topic 3: Identification of *E. coli* serogroups using real time and conventional PCR
- Topic 4: *stx* subtyping of STEC strains

6. Training Format and Methodology

The in-person training consists of a three-day course that includes an overview of the laboratory procedures and introduction to pathogenic *E. coli*.

Each group of pathogenic *E. coli* is characterized by specific marker genes that can be present on chromosomes or plasmids. During the training, the participants will assay unknown *E. coli* strains for the presence of different pathogroup virulence genes by real-time PCR. The STEC strains identified will be further characterised for the *stx* subtype possessed and for a subset of serogroups, by means of real-time or conventional PCR.

All three days include explanatory discussions driven by the EURL-STEC experts and practical sessions carried out by the trainee with a hands-on approach, under the supervision of the EURL-VTEC staff.

7. Draft Agenda

DAY 1 (14:00-17:30)

Overview of the activities and procedures

Opening discussion on the work-plan and overview of the activities to be done during the training.

Preparation of DNA templates from unknown *E. coli* test strains.

Real-time PCR for the identification of the STEC, EIEC, EAEC and ETEC *E. coli* pathogroups.

DAY 2 (9:30-17:00)

Evaluation of real-time PCR results.

Molecular serogrouping of STEC strains by conventional PCR and agarose gel electrophoresis to visualise the results.

stx-subtyping assay by conventional PCR and agarose gel electrophoresis to visualise the *stx*-subtyping PCR results.

DAY 3 (9:30-15:00)

Evaluation of the serogroups determination *stx*-subtyping PCR results.

Further molecular serogrouping of STEC by real-time PCR.

Analysis of the results obtained.

General discussion on the activities carried out.

8. Participant Selection Criteria

The participant should have a professional background as a microbiologist or technician, be employed on a permanent contract, and work for a national public health institute. The participants will be nominated by the NFPs for Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses or OCPs for Microbiology within the EURL Network. Participation of non-NFPs or non-OCPs is possible if they are employed within their respective institutions, i.e. that are staff members of the network laboratories, and their participation will be agreed with ECDC. Basic knowledge of diarrheagenic *E. coli* is expected. Proficiency in English is essential for effective communication and participation.

9. Invitation Procedure

The invitation will be distributed through the NFPs for Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses and OCPs for Microbiology within the Laboratory Network of the EURL-PH-FWDB.

Each country may nominate two candidates, one primary and one secondary candidate. The secondary candidate may be selected if places remain available or may serve as a reserve for the primary candidate. Participant selection will be carried out by an independent committee of EURL-FWD training organisers, who will assess applications based on predefined criteria.

Applicants will be asked to submit a motivation letter outlining their training needs and the relevance of the course. They will also be required to complete a questionnaire covering their background, experience, role within the national system, and the possibilities for implementing the course at their own institute. Non-NCPs and non-OCPs will be required to submit a letter of support from their NCP or OCP.

The course is expected to accommodate 20 participants (10 participants in each session). The application deadline is April 17, 2026.

10. Training Evaluation Plan

10.1 Evaluation Objectives

- Assess participant satisfaction
- Assess achievement of learning objectives
- Identify areas for improvement

10.2 Evaluation Methods

Participants will fill out a learning questionnaire at the end of the training. Those who successfully complete the questionnaire, achieving at least 80% compliance, will be awarded a certificate of achievement of the training objectives. If this threshold is not reached, a simple certificate of attendance will be issued, and possible follow-up actions will be agreed with the participant.

Upon completion of the training, a trainee satisfaction questionnaire will be distributed to all participants. Certificate of attendance (or certificate of achievement) will only be issued to participants who have completed the evaluation form.

10.3 Use of Evaluation Results

The evaluations help support internal quality improvement by showing how participants experienced the different parts of the course and where changes may be needed. In addition, feedback from both participants and the EURL-FWD network can be used to guide adjustments to future trainings, including the selection of topics and the overall design of the programme. The training outcomes and evaluation results will be reported in annual progress report of the EURL.

11. Training Materials and Dissemination

The organiser confirms that:

- All relevant training materials (presentations, exercises, guidance documents, supporting materials) will be made available electronically to the relevant network members after the execution of the training activity.
- Materials will be shared via the [ECON EURL for FWDB collaboration site](#) (NFPs and OCPs) and via email (non-NFPs and non-OCPs)
- Any confidential or restricted materials will be handled according to agreed procedures.

12. Logistical Arrangements

- Course dates:

Session A (10 participants): 07-09-2026 to 09-09-2026

Session B (10 participants): 14-09-2026 to 16-09-2026

- Venue details and address:

Istituto Superiore di Sanità

Piazzale Valerio Massimo, n. 5, 00161 Rome, Italy

this is not the main entrance of ISS but it is the closest to the building n. 21 where the training will take place.

- Travel and accommodation arrangements (if applicable):

The EURL-PH-FWDB will cover travel and accommodation costs by providing pre-paid economy air tickets and pre-paid hotel

- Administrative support: Guendalina Fornari Luswergh will be available for any administrative support

13. Annexes

- Annex 1: Draft Invitation Letter

Annex 1 – Draft Invitation Letter

Dear NFPs for Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses and OCPs for Microbiology,

On behalf of the EURL-PH-FWDB team, we are pleased to invite you to our in-person training programme for 2026.

Training 1: Basic short-read data analysis, Salmonella serotyping and cluster analysis

Date: 3–4 June 2026

Location: National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), Bilthoven, Netherlands

Capacity: 25 participants

The course aims to develop practical skills in working with whole genome sequencing (WGS) data and to improve understanding of bioinformatics tools used to process short-read sequencing data. These tools will be applied to Salmonella serotyping, AMR detection, and to demonstrate how cluster analysis can be performed for epidemiological purposes. The training will strengthen participants' capabilities for routine laboratory surveillance and enhance preparedness for potential outbreak investigations.

Target audience: This training is intended for microbiologists and technicians at public health institutes involved in Salmonella outbreak detections who are interested in the full WGS workflow, from laboratory background to cluster analysis. No prior WGS experience is required, as the course starts at an introductory level.

Travel: Expected arrival on Tuesday the 2nd of June and return to your home country on Thursday 4th of June in the evening.

Training 2: Identification and characterization of pathogenic *Escherichia coli*

Dates:

- Session A: 7–9 September 2026
- Session B: 14–16 September 2026

Location: Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS), Rome, Italy

Capacity: 20 participants (10 per session)

Session A and B are identical. The course aims to develop practical skills to identify and characterise diarrhoeagenic *Escherichia coli*, with a particular focus on Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC).

Target audience: This training is intended for microbiologists and technicians at public health institutes involved in the diagnosis of diarrhoeagenic *E. coli* infections and the characterisation of STEC and other pathotypes, including Enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), and Enteroaggregative *E. coli* (EAEC). This course includes practical laboratory exercises.

Travel: Expected arrival on the 7th of September (for session A) and the 14th of September (session B) and return to your home country the 9th of September (session A) and 16th of September (session B).

Application Procedure

Participants are invited to apply for one or both trainings in 2026. Each Member State may nominate up to two candidates per course (one primary and one secondary).

[Link to online application form for Training 1](#)

[Link to online application form for Training 2](#)

The application deadline is **17 April 2026 for both trainings**.

In the application form, candidates are requested to submit:

- A motivation letter describing their role, relevance to the training, and intended use of the skills
- For non-NFP/OCP applicants: a letter of support from the NFP

Soon after, selected participants will be contacted directly and will be provided with practical information about the reservation of flight tickets and accommodation. The EURL-PH-FWDB project will cover the expenses related to travel, accommodation, and per diem.

We look forward to your participation.

On behalf of the EURL-PH-FWDB team

European Union Reference Laboratory for Public Health on Food- and Waterborne Bacteria

General email: Train-EURL-PH-FWDB@ssi.dk

EURL for FWDB collaboration site: [Home](#)

STATENS
SERUM
INSTITUT

National Institute for Public Health
and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

Document review / approval (the coordinator)

Name	Role	Action (review / approval)	Date
David Canovas Jorda	Project officer (HaDEA)	approval	04/05/2026